

Pseudohalogen Character of Fluorosulphate Group in Iron(II) and (III) Fluorosulphates

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Manuscript received 24 August 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

Fluorosulphate groups in iron(II) and (III) fluorosulphates act as tri- and bidentate ligands respectively as is evident from their i.r. spectra. $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_2$ forms 1 : 2 adducts with pyridine and ethylenediamine and 1 : 1 adducts with *o*-chloroaniline and triphenylphosphine oxide. The diffuse reflectance spectra and the magnetic moment values of the parent fluorosulphates and their coordination complexes indicate that iron is hexacoordinated in these compounds. The pyridine complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_2 \cdot 3\text{Py}$ has a magnetic moment of 39 B.M. and might be magnetically non-dilute compound. The i. r. spectra of the complexes reveal C_3 symmetry of the fluorosulphate groups and the nature of the coordination of the ligands.

COORDINATION complexes of some metal halosulphates with pyridine¹, ammonia² and acetonitrile³ have been reported. Coordination complexes of iron(II) and (III) halides with various ligands are also well known⁴. The work on the chemistry of halosulphates⁵⁻⁹ has amply brought out the pseudohalogen character of the halosulphate group. To further substantiate the pseudohalogen character of the fluorosulphate group, we report in this communication the preparation and the characterization of the coordination complexes of iron(II) and (III) fluorosulphates with pyridine, ethylenediamine, orthochloroaniline, anthranilic acid, triphenylphosphine oxide and dimethylsulphoxide. The vibrational spectral modes of the fluorosulphate group are enormously changed when the ligands coordinate to these metal fluorosulphates.

Experimental

Fluorosulphuric acid was prepared and purified as reported earlier⁶. Pyridine, ethylenediamine and dimethylsulphoxide were kept over potassium hydroxide pellets for 24 hr and distilled before use. Anthranilic acid was recrystallised from solvent ether. Orthochloroaniline (German repacked) and triphenylphosphine oxide (E. Merck AR) were used as such. Iron(II) and (III) fluorosulphates were prepared as described^{10,11}.

Iron, sulphur and fluorine were determined gravimetrically as Fe_2O_3 , BaSO_4 and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{SnF}$ respectively. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically.

Preparation of Complexes : The ligand (pyridine, ethylenediamine or *o*-chloroaniline) was added

dropwise to a known weight of the respective fluorosulphate suspended in carbontetrachloride in 1 : 2 mole ratio. The contents were stirred magnetically for 3-4 hr. The complexes formed were filtered, washed with CCl_4 and dried in vacuo. In case of adducts with triphenylphosphine oxide or anthranilic acid, dry ether was used as the reaction medium, the remaining procedure was the same. The stoichiometry of the complexes remained the same even when the ligands were taken in excess. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Physical Measurements : The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded as nujol or hexachlorobutadene mulls in silver chloride and polythene plates using Perkin-Elmer 621 double-grating spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities of the compounds were determined at room temperature using Guoy's method. Diffuse reflectance spectra in the range 5-50 kK of powdered complexes were recorded on the SP-7N Spectrophotometer fitted with a standard reflectance attachment using magnesium oxide as the reference.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic Properties and Electronic Spectra : The magnetic moment values of iron(II) complexes are in the range 5.4-5.7 B. M. which is in conformity with the expected values for pseudo-octahedral iron(II) complexes¹².

The two bands assigned to ${}^6E_g \leftarrow {}^6T_{2g}$ (Table 2) transitions in the reflectance spectra of these complexes also suggest their octahedral configuration.

High spin iron(III) complexes have magnetic moments close to the spin only value of 5.9 B. M.¹³.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, COLOR AND MELTING POINTS OF IRON(II) AND (III) FLUOROSULPHATES AND ITS COORDINATION COMPLEXES WITH OXYGEN AND NITROGEN DONORS

Complex	Color	Melting Point (°C)	*Analytical Data					
			Fe	S	F	O	H	N
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂	bluish grey	>270	21.30 (22.00)	26.50 (25.21)	15.80 (14.97)	— (—)	— (—)	— (—)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .2Py	dirty yellow	>270	14.50 (13.55)	15.03 (15.54)	10.60 (9.22)	29.60 (29.13)	2.60 (2.42)	5.80 (6.79)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .2En	dirty green	decomposed 190-195	14.60 (14.97)	16.00 (17.11)	10.90 (10.16)	19.40 (12.83)	4.60 (4.28)	14.62 (14.97)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ CINH ₂	grey	decomposed 200	14.10 (14.64)	15.60 (16.78)	10.60 (9.96)	19.40 (18.88)	1.70 (1.57)	3.65 (3.67)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO	steel grey	decomposed 175-183	11.80 (10.50)	11.99 (12.03)	6.90 (7.14)	41.20 (40.60)	2.70 (2.82)	— (—)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂	pale-green grey	>270	14.90 (15.82)	28.90 (27.20)	17.80 (16.15)	— (—)	— (—)	— (—)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .3Py	light yellow	>270	9.50 (9.46)	15.90 (16.26)	10.60 (9.66)	30.72 (30.51)	2.80 (2.54)	7.30 (7.12)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ CINH ₂	black	>270	11.95 (11.65)	19.10 (19.98)	12.70 (11.86)	14.40 (14.99)	1.40 (1.25)	3.10 (3.91)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂ COOH	dirty brown	>270	12.50 (11.40)	19.10 (19.59)	12.10 (11.63)	16.80 (17.14)	1.60 (1.42)	2.60 (2.85)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO	greenish yellow	>270	9.70 (8.85)	14.00 (15.21)	8.40 (9.03)	35.60 (34.23)	2.60 (2.37)	— (—)

* The values in the parenthesis are those of required.

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF IRON(II) FLUOROSULPHATE AND ITS COORDINATION COMPLEXES

Complex	⁵ E _g ← ⁵ T _{2g} (kK)	μ_{eff} (BM)
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂	7.02 13.15	5.6
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .2Py	7.42 13.86	5.6
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .2En	7.92 14.29	5.4
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ CINH ₂	6.66 15.62	5.4
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO	6.45 14.92	5.5

The magnetic moment value of iron(III) fluorosulphate at room temperature has been found to be 5.4 B. M. This slightly lower value suggests both ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic coupling in the compound. The complexes of iron(III) fluorosulphate have magnetic moment in the range 4.9-5.4 B. M. (Table 3) suggesting the octahedral geometry. The pyridine complex, which has

assigned to ⁶A_{1g}(t_{2g} - π*) and charge transfer band (π - π*) indicate high spin octahedral environment around iron(III) (ref. 15). In iron(III) fluorosulphate complexes the observed absorption maxima (Table 3) also indicate octahedral environment around iron(III) in these complexes.

Infrared Spectra: The fluorosulphate group in iron(II) fluorosulphate has a C_{3v} symmetry, in which all the three oxygen atoms of a fluorosulphate group are coordinated to iron in an equivalent manner. In iron(III) fluorosulphate the symmetry is C_s and the fluorosulphate groups act as bidentate ligands¹¹. Iron is, thus, hexacoordinated in these fluorosulphates. The perusal of Tables 4 and 5 reveal that the fluorosulphate groups in various coordination complexes have C_s symmetry. The electronic spectra of iron(III) fluorosulphate and its coordination complexes reveal the hexacoordination

TABLE 3—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA (kK) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (BM) OF IRON(III) FLUOROSULPHATE AND ITS COORDINATION COMPLEXES

Complex	³ T _{1g} ← ⁴ A _{1g} (G)	³ T _{2g} ← ⁴ A _{1g} (G)	⁶ A _{1g} (t _{2g} - π*)	(π - e _g)	(π - π*)	μ_{eff}
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂	—	—	23.25	—	41.00	5.4
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .3Py	14.92	21.27	—	27.77	—	3.9
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ CINH ₂	13.88	21.27	—	28.57	—	5.2
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂ COOH	—	18.49	—	27.72	—	5.2
Fe(SO ₂ F) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO	14.70	21.85	25.00	—	—	4.9

unusual magnetic moment of 3.9 B. M. can be considered as magnetically non-dilute iron(III) compound¹⁴. In iron(III) fluorosulphate, the absorption maxima at 23.2 and 41.0 kK (Table 3)

of iron. The magnitude of S-O stretching frequencies¹⁶ reveals the monodentate nature of fluorosulphate groups in Fe(SO₂F)₂.3Py. The infrared spectra of Fe(SO₂F)₂.C₆H₅NH₂COOH

TABLE 4—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF IRON(II) FLUOROSULPHATE(A) AND ITS COORDINATION COMPLEXES

(A)	(A)2Py	(A)2En	(A)C ₆ H ₄ ClNH ₂	(A)(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ N-O	Assignments
1261	1336	1290-1270b	1300	1320	$\nu_4(E)$
	1212		1250	1235	
1118	1103	1100b	1125	1150	$\nu_1(A_1)$
862	782	780	750	752	$\nu_2(A_1)$
610	672	660	642	660	$\nu_3(E)$
	595	630	620	620	
568	570	550	555	540	$\nu_5(A_1)$
419	470	460	480	480	$\nu_6(E)$
	365	390	440	360	
	440				$\nu_{1,eb}$
	620				ν_{ea}
	1610				ν_{ga}
	1602				
	3305		3425		$\nu_{asy(N-H)}$
	3294		3240		$\delta_{sy(N-H)}$
	3290		1615		$\delta(N-H)$
	3245			1460	$\nu(P-C)$
	3180			1020	
				1115	$\nu(P=O)$

The perusal of the infrared spectrum of $Fe(SO_3F)_2 \cdot 2Py$ indicate the bidentate nature of the fluorosulphate groups, whereas in other cases the fluorosulphate groups also have C_2 symmetry.

In liquid pyridine the 16b vibration (an out-of-plane ring deformation) is at 403 cm^{-1} while the 6a and 8a vibrations (in-plane ring deformations) are at 601 and 1578 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁸. These three bands show significant shifts to higher frequencies (Tables 4 and 5) indicating coordination of pyridine to iron in the pyridine complexes. In ethylenediamine N-H appears at 3305 , 3290 and 3190 cm^{-1} and all these frequencies are lowered in the complex $Fe(SO_3F)_2 \cdot 2En$ (Table 4). In addition to the lowered ν_{N-H} , the frequencies at 3305 and 3190 cm^{-1} are also observed which indicate that only one of the nitrogens of ethylenediamine is coordinated to the metal. Important vibrations for *o*-chloroaniline are 3440 (ν_{N-H}), 3360 (ν_{N-H}), 1618 (N-H bend), 1240 (C-N def.) and 1050 (N-H twist). The ring vibrations appear at 1600 , 1500 and 1468 cm^{-1} (ref. 19). When nitrogen of *o*-chloroaniline is coordinated to metal, the major changes are found

 TABLE 5—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF $Fe(SO_3F)_2$ (B) AND ITS COORDINATION COMPLEXES

B	B.3Py	B.C ₆ H ₄ ClNH ₂	B.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂ COOH	B.(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO	Assignments
1360	1420	1395	1400	1340	$\nu_4(E)$
1137	1270	1300	1300	1215	
			1290		
			1220		
1090	1115	1040	1090	1070	$\nu_1(A_1)$
			940		
850	750	750	770		
			748	742	$\nu_2(A_1)$
			720		
630	680	680	685	665	$\nu_3(E)$
579	579	570	580	568	
551	560	545	560	550	$\nu_4(A_1)$
419	470	450	482	480	$\nu_6(E)$
318	409	380		435	
	429				$\nu_{1,eb}$
	639				ν_{ea}
	1610				ν_{ga}
		3420			$\nu_{as(N-H)}$
		3235			$\nu_{sy(N-H)}$
		1618			$\delta(N-H)$
			3420		$\nu_{as(N-H)}$
			1715		$\nu(G=O)$
				1455	
				1040	ν_{P-C}
				1115	$\nu_{P=O}$

has two doublets in the S-O stretching range (1400 , 1300 and 1290 , 1220) and two bands around 800 cm^{-1} (ν_{S-F}). This may indicate the presence of two non-equivalent fluorosulphate groups. This type of situation has been observed earlier in case of some other fluorosulphates such as $Sr(SO_3F)_2$, $Sn(SO_3F)_2$ and $Pb(SO_3F)_2$.¹⁷ The hexacoordination of iron in this complex which is suggested from its electronic spectra make us to infer that two of the fluorosulphate groups are bidentate while the third is monodentate.

in the ν_{N-H} . Both asymmetric and symmetric ν_{N-H} are lowered. In the complexes $Fe(SO_3F)_2 \cdot C_6H_4ClNH_2$ and $Fe(SO_3F)_2 \cdot C_6H_4ClNH_2$, the symmetric N-H stretch is lower by *ca.* 120 cm^{-1} while the lowering in the asymmetric stretch is of lower magnitude. This indicates that nitrogen of *o*-chloroaniline is coordinated to iron in these complexes. The ring vibrations are reproduced in the complexes with slight changes in their positions (Tables 4 and 5). Anthranilic acid may coordinate either through its carbonyl oxygen or through amino nitrogen.

Coordination through oxygen will decrease the double bond character of the carbonyl group, resulting in a decrease in $\nu_{(C=O)}$. Coordination through nitrogen, on the other hand, would increase the double bond character of the carbonyl group with a consequent increase in its stretching frequency. The ν_{N-H} in pure anthranilic acid appears at 3480 and 3370 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{(C=O)}$ at 1665 cm^{-1} . A band at 1715 cm^{-1} in $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot \text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2\text{COOH}$ rules out the possibility of donation through carbonyl oxygen. The coordination may, therefore, be through the nitrogen of the amino group. Moreover, the lowering of the ν_{N-H} in the complex (Table 5) substantiates this view. Coordination of triphenylphosphine oxide occurs through its oxygen as a result of which $\nu_{(P=O)}$ is lowered and $\nu_{(P-C)}$ is raised in the complexes²⁰. The lowering of $\nu_{(P=O)}$ is of the order of *ca.* 80 cm^{-1} in these complexes.

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